

Bank Mega Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Mega Syariah and Conventional Banks using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key words " Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Mega Syariah and Conventional Banks based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 6 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; and (6) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Mega Syariah and Conventional Banks, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

The banking sector in Indonesia plays an important role as a financial institution which is at the heart of the country's economy. Banking is very crucial in maintaining economic stability because it acts as a financial intermediary (intermediation institution) (Fahrrial in Setiawati, 2020). The banking system is regulated in Law no. 10 of 1998, where commercial banks are banks that run their business based on traditional or sharia principles and provide financial services (Setiawati, 2020).

Basically, conventional and sharia financial institutions have almost similar tasks, namely collecting and distributing funds. However, the significant difference lies in the way the profits are distributed. Conventional banks use an interest system, while Islamic banks use a profit-sharing system (division based on profits and losses). Islamic banks do not use the principle of interest because Islam prohibits usury, which is contained in this principle. Other differences are also related to legal aspects, organizational form, company financing products, and work environment (Irham, 2019).

One of the financial institutions in Indonesia is Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional. These two banks are popular financial institutions in Indonesia, which are under the auspices of PT Mega Corpora and have a parent company called CT Corpora. Bank Mega Syariah, which was originally called PT Bank

General Tugu (Bank Tugu), was acquired by PT Mega Corpora, then on July 27 2004 PT Mega Corpora changed its activities from conventional to sharia. Meanwhile, Bank Mega was built under the name PT Bank Karman in 1969 and changed its name to PT Mega Bank in 1992, then in 2000 the name was changed to PT Bank Mega (Supriyatna, 2018).

The popularity of Mega Syariah and Conventional Banks continues to increase from year to year, this can be seen from the many scientific articles that review Mega Syariah and Conventional Banks as the main topic. In mid-2022, there were 13 scientific articles covering Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional, with most of the articles coming from Indonesian management journals. In several studies, Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional are often compared with several other sharia and conventional banks. Usually, researchers only study analyzes such as health analysis, strategy analysis, and product analysis. However, there has been no research that specifically examines the development map of Mega Syariah and Conventional Banks as financial institutions.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Mega on Sharia Financial Inclusion using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding Bank Mega, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Mega, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Bank Mega or PT Bank Karman, which was founded in 1969, is one of the largest companies in Indonesia that focuses on banking and financial services. Bank Mega is trusted as a solution to solve the problem of capital needs for people who want to start or run their business, but are hampered by funding problems (Milniati at. al. 2022). Meanwhile, Bank Mega Syariah is a sharia agency that operates in the financial sector, with all its activities based on Islamic regulations. The products and services offered must comply with the principles of Islamic law (Busnita, 2022).

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can

be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications (Dubyna et al., 2022) .

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The research object is Mega Syariah and Conventional Banks. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Bank Mega originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Bank Mega " for the entire year (2009 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings, and research space based on library research.

Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses research mapping on Mega Sharia and Conventional Banks in Financial Institutions through VOSviewer bibliometric

studies and Library Researchs. Based on a search for scientific publications on the Garuda website for 14 years, namely 2009 to 2022, there are 134 articles discussing Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional.

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional

Search results for scientific publications about Mega Sharia and Conventional Banks from 2009 to 2022 show an increase and decrease in the number of article publications each year. The highest number of scientific publications occurred in 2021, with 19 articles, more than in 2020 which only had 15 articles. In total there are 134 article publication titles about Mega Syariah and Conventional Banks, with an average of 10 scientific publication articles about Mega Syariah and Conventional Banks every year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Journal Article Publication	Year of Publication	Journal Article Publication
2009	1	2014	5	2019	11
2010	2	2015	10	2020	15
2011	1	2016	10	2021	19
2012	5	2017	13	2022	13
2013	11	2018	18		
Total 134					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 2 shows that there are 13 institutions that occupy the top 3 positions as institutions with the highest number of publications. JIM (Journal of Indonesian Management) is an affiliate/journal publishing institution that publishes research results on Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional with the highest number of publications in first position, namely 4 articles.

Table 2. Affiliation/institution of journal publishers about Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
JIM (Journal of Indonesian Management)	4
FEB Student Scientific Journal	3
Al-Mashrafiyah (Journal of Sharia Economics, Finance and Banking), MASLAHAH (Journal of Islamic Law and Sharia Banking), HJABE (Hasanuddin Journal of Applied Business and Entrepreneurship), IQTISHODUNA (Journal of Islamic Economics), USU Civil Law Journal, EMBA (Research Journal Economics, Management, Business and Accounting), Journal of Sharia Banking and Finance, JOM (Student Online Journal) in the Field of	2

Economics, Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals, Premise Law Journal, Tadayun (Journal of Sharia Economic Law).

Source: Data processed, Microsoft Escel 20 16.

Table 3 shows that the most productive researcher on Mega Sharia and Conventional Banks is Mustopa Kamal Rokan from the State Islamic University of North Sumatra, with 3 published articles.

Table 3. Researcher productivity regarding Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional

Researcher	Number of Publications
Mustopa Kamal Rokan (North Sumatra State Islamic University)	3
Abdul Jalil (Datokarama State Islamic Institute, Palu), Ahmad Maulidizen (University of Malay), Dzabir Hamzah (Hasanudin University), Andi Rosano (Bina Sarana Informatics University).	2
(Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Rohimah et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Emiliani et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Zahro et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rahmawati et al., 2023) (Shalsabila et al., 2023) (Fitriawati et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Febrian & Budianto, 2023) (Rohmah et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023)	

Source: Data processed, Microsoft Excel 20 16.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Mega Sharia and Conventional Banks

Based on search results on the Garuda website, there are 134 research articles discussing Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional. Then, the 134 articles were exported in RIS format and input and analyzed using VOSviewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional

- Cluster 5. Purple, there are 11 topics, namely: assets, capital adequacy ratio, data analysis, deposit ratio, ibank, loan, performing loan, PT Bank Mega, PT Bank Mega Tbk, return, value.
- Cluster 6. Light blue, there are 9 topics, namely: customer loyalty, customer statistics, F test, internal control, multiple linear regression, quality, reliability, persistent quality, T test.
- Orange color, there are 7 topics, namely: analysis, burnout, emotional intelligence, goals, research, significant influence, work performance.
- Cluster 8. Brown color, there are 6 topics, namely: Bank BNI Syariah, Bank Indonesia, Bank Mega Syariah, procedure, product, service.
- Cluster 9. Pink, there are 4 topics, namely: Bank Mega, Bank Mega Tbk, Megafirst customers, Persero.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Mega's Financial Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 10 topics related to the financial performance of Bank Mega Conventional, namely:

1. First, the influence of profit optimization, Third Party Funds/DPK, interest rates, liquidity ratios, credit risk, operational risk, and credit/loan distribution on profitability.
2. Second, the influence of the quality of internal control in the accounting information system on the reliability of the audit trail.
3. Third, the influence of Earning Per Share/EPS on share prices.
4. Fourth, the influence of financial distress on financial ratios.
5. Fifth, financial performance uses Risk-Based Bank Rating/RBBR and PSAK 71.
6. Sixth, the influence of capital structure and BI rate on company value.
7. Seventh, the influence of Return On Assets/ROA and Non Performing Loans/NPL on the Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR.
8. Eighth, the influence of Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Current Ratio/CR, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, and Operational Expenses on Operating Income/BOPO on Return On Assets/ROA.
9. Ninth, the influence of Non-Performing Loans/NPL and Bank Indonesia interest rates on net profit.
10. Tenth, application of the Debt to Equity Ratio/DER.

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 14 topics related to Bank Mega Syariah's financial performance, namely:

1. First, the influence of Productive Asset Quality/KAP and capital adequacy on profitability.
2. Second, financial performance using the Bank Indonesia Regulation no. 9/1/PBI/2007 and Balanced Scorecard.
3. Third, the level of efficiency using the DEA method and comparison of financial ratios.
4. Fourth, the influence of the profitability ratio on Murabahah margin income.
5. Fifth, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Non Performing Financing/NPF, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, and Non Performing Loans/NPL on Return On Assets/ROA.
6. Sixth, health level using the CAMEL and RGEC methods.
7. Seventh, Mudharabah accounting with PSAK No. 105.

8. Eighth, the influence of Murabahah financing, Mudharabah financing, equity, Third Party Funds/TPF, operational costs and cost of credit on net profit.
9. Ninth, financial reports predict the likelihood of bankruptcy.
10. Tenth, the influence of currency exchange rates, working capital financing with a Musyarakah agreement, the quality of the financing portfolio, and inflation on profitability.
11. Eleventh, the influence of asset quality, solvency ratio, profitability ratio and liquidity ratio on financial performance.
12. Twelfth, the influence of Return On Assets/ROA, Operational Costs on Operating Income/BOPO, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Non Performing Financing/NPF on Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR.
13. Thirteenth, the influence of Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR on corporate image.
14. Fourteenth, the solvency ratio uses the ARIMA BOX-JENKINS method.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Mega Employee Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 30 topics related to the performance of Bank Mega Conventional and Sharia employees, namely:

1. Organizational culture;
2. Burnout;
3. Discipline;
4. E-Learning;
5. Leadership style;
6. Incentive;
7. Compensation;
8. Job satisfaction;
9. Individual characteristics;
10. Job characteristics;
11. Organizational commitment;
12. Compensation;
13. Emotional intelligence;
14. Interpersonal communication;
15. Human resource competency;
16. Role conflict;
17. Self control;
18. Work environment;
19. Loyalty;
20. Work motivation;
21. Quality of service;
22. Psychological capital;
23. Management knowledge;
24. Training;
25. Development;
26. Job promotion;
27. Job stress;
28. Organizational structure;
29. Talent management;
30. Work pressure.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Mega Customer Behavior

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 25 topics related to Bank Mega Conventional and Sharia customer behavior, namely:

1. Internal audit;
2. Profit sharing;
3. Sharia marketing mix;
4. Brands;
5. Customer relationship marketing;
6. Work ethics;
7. Internet banking/IBANK with One-Time Password/OTP.
8. Number of tellers;
9. Credit card;
10. Religious beliefs;
11. Satisfaction;
12. Trust;
13. Ease of use;
14. Location;
15. Benefit;
16. Charter model;
17. Mark;
18. Service;
19. Product;
20. Promotion;
21. Relationship marketing;
22. Attitude;
23. Queuing system;
24. Marketing system;
25. Satisfaction information system.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Mega Financing/Credit Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 5 research topics related to Bank Mega Conventional financing products, namely:

1. First, legal protection for customers in business credit due to confiscation of execution of Building Use Rights/HGB.
2. Second, resolving bad/problematic credit disputes in cases of default, such as credit card agreements.
3. Third, the application of the principle of balance in credit agreements.
4. Fourth, the suitability of prospective credit card customers using the C4.5 Algorithm method.
5. Fifth, collateral/guarantees in the distribution of Murabahah contract financing.

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 8 research topics related to Bank Mega Syariah financing products, namely:

1. First, bank agency in Murabahah and Wakalah financing.
2. Second, the effect of profit sharing financing on profitability.
3. Third, the influence of communication and resources on credit policy.

4. Fourth, Sharia Home Ownership Credit/KPR financing, such as Covid-19, Wakalah contracts.
5. Fifth, resolving sharia problematic/non-performing loans in religious courts.
6. Sixth, efficiency of credit distribution using the Data Envelopment Analysis/DEA approach.
7. Seventh, the accounting treatment of Musyarakah contracts is based on PSAK 106.
8. Eighth, binding mortgage rights to Musyarakah financing.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Mega Savings Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 1 research topic relates to Bank Mega Syariah savings/deposit products, namely: marketing strategy for savings services.

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 6 research topics related to Bank Mega Syariah savings/deposit products, namely:

1. First, accounting treatment of Hajj savings and critical analysis.
2. Second, the sharia gold pawning system and procedures.
3. Third, the savings plan product agreement.
4. Fourth, the application of the wadiah contract to current account products.
5. Fifth, the application of profit sharing calculations based on the equivalent rate for Mudharabah savings.
6. Sixth, the Mudharabah savings contract is based on DSN-MUI fatwa no. 115 of 2017.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues at Bank Mega

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 7 research topics related to issues at Bank Mega, namely:

1. First, the IT disaster recovery plan strategy for the core banking system using the Analytical Hierarchy Process/AHP approach.
2. Second, responsibility accounting information in assessing manager performance.
3. Third, the application of article 20 paragraph (2) A and PBI No. 11/25/PBI/2009 concerning risk management of opening accounts without customers.
4. Fourth, the formation of a sensitivity gap.
5. Fifth, executive information system.
6. Sixth, Bank Mega Syariah's social performance.
7. Seventh, implementation of the Qardh contract.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Bank Mega Syariah and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; and (6) Other issues.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>

- Quadratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni*, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>